

Range and mean values of spikelet fertility in parents and F₁s (indica/japonica), 1995 wet season.

Parent/F ₁	Fertility (%)	
	Range	Mean + SE
<i>Parents</i>		
Kagalikai	73.1 - 89.7	85.7 + 2.9
Fukumishi	83.7 - 95.2	88.3 + 1.8
Siam 2	91.3 - 98.1	95.7 + 1.2
Toride	77.7 - 98.0	92.1 + 3.7
JD5	95.3 - 97.8	86.7 + 0.4
JD6	81.1 - 93.3	87.2 + 2.1
JD8	77.8 - 95.4	88.8 + 3.0
Heera	56.4 - 86.6	73.8 + 5.1
PNR 381	87.5 - 96.0	92.8 + 1.4
Dular	91.1 - 97.0	95.0 + 1.0
N22	89.2-100.0	93.5 + 2.0
<i>F₁s</i>		
Kagalikai/JD5	63.0 - 71.5	68.6 + 1.8
Kagalikai/JD6	55.0 - 69.8	61.3 + 2.6
Kagalikai/JD8	73.1 - 81.9	78.2 + 3.5
Kagalikai/Heera	61.1 - 70.1	66.1 + 1.8
Kagalikai/PNR381	47.6 - 65.7	52.8 + 3.5
Kagalikai/Dular	81.9 - 90.5	83.6 + 2.4
Kagalikai/N22	80.6 - 90.1	86.0 + 1.7
Fukumishi/JD5	40.4 - 70.4	57.2 + 5.4
Fukumishi/JD6	22.2 - 57.3	43.1 + 6.7
Fukumishi/JD8 ^a	74.1 - 81.3	77.7 + 1.3
Fukumishi/Heera	48.0 - 55.0	56.0 + 3.9
Fukumishi/PNR381	37.4 - 66.3	47.2 + 5.4
Fukumishi/Dular	83.2 - 93.1	87.8 + 1.9
Fukumishi/N22	-	-
Siam 2/JD5	64.2 - 89.7	74.0 + 4.9
Siam 2/JD6	52.5 - 67.6	59.4 + 2.9
Siam 2/JD8	69.9 - 78.3	74.1 + 1.7
Siam 2/Heera	-	-
Siam 2/PNR381	47.1 - 62.0	54.6 + 2.6
Siam 2/Dular	80.4 - 96.9	90.0 + 2.9
Siam 2/N22	78.6 - 90.8	83.4 + 2.4
Toride/JD5	48.7 - 65.2	56.0 + 2.8
Toride/JD6	38.8 - 48.2	42.3 + 1.8
Toride/JD8 ^a	74.0 - 82.0	78.3 + 1.6
Toride/Heera	45.3 - 51.4	47.7 + 1.2
Toride/PNR381	35.2 - 49.5	41.7 + 2.4
Toride/Dular	83.5 - 94.6	90.7 + 1.9
Toride/N22	80.0 - 90.5	83.8 + 2.0

^aObservations from 1996 wet season.

Toride and Siam 2. The spikelet fertility range indicated the presence of WC gene(s) in JD8.

The performance of JD8 was comparable with that of the two WC varieties, Dular and N22. JD8 has an advantage over traditional N22 or Dular because of its earliness and improved plant type. Studies at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, indicated that JD8 is a probable maintainer of cytoplasmic male sterile lines with wide abortiveness and has potential use in hybrid rice breeding involving tropical japonica restorers.

Evaluation of EMC models for fitting sorption isotherms for rough rice, brown rice, and milled rice

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Studies were conducted to apply equilibrium moisture content (EMC) models to sorption data of rough rice, brown rice, and milled rice (3.8%, 6.6%, and 10.3% degree of polish) of hybrid variety Pant Sankar Dhan 1. Experiments were planned using three temperature levels (20, 30, and 40 °C) and seven water activity levels ranging from 0.112 to 0.962.

The static desiccator method was used to obtain sorption data. Values obtained were plotted against respective relative humidities to get sorption isotherms.

One 3-parameter and five 2-parameter EMC models were tested for their sustainability in predicting EMC. The actual and linearized models are shown below.

Statistical parameters such as coefficient of determination (R²), standard error (SE₂), root mean square deviation (s), and mean relative percentage deviation (p) were computed to compare the ability of selected models to fit experimental sorption data.

Bradley's equation fitted the data of all samples in the water activity range of 0.30-0.80, both in adsorption and desorption processes for all selected temperature ranges.

For rough rice, Oswin's equation failed to explain the sorption data below the water activity level of 0.30 and above 0.75 at all temperature ranges. The model also failed to fit the data of brown rice and milled rice at high temperatures.

Like Bradley's equation, Smith's equation failed to explain sorption data of samples in lower and higher water activity levels. For both rough rice and brown rice, the residual value of EMC was maximum at water activity levels of 0.112 and above 0.633, respectively. Hence, for rough rice and brown rice, the best zone in which Smith's equation fits is the 0.33-0.633 level. For milled rice with 3.8%, 6.6%, and 10.3% degree of polish, Smith's equation showed a poor fit.

Of the five 2-parameter models applied to the experimental data, Henderson's model gave the best fit to the experimental data—its p, s, and SE₂ values were comparatively smaller than the others, and R₂ was the highest (Table 1).

Among the one 3-parameter and five 2-parameter models tested, the p value calculated for GAB's equation was the lowest (below 5) and the R² value was greater than 99% (Table 2). On the basis of lowest p and highest R², this equation best fitted all samples in the experiment.

EMC model	Actual form	Linear form
Bradley	$1n(1/a_w) = A \times B^{M_e}$	$1n(1n(1/a_w)) = 1n(A) + M_e \times 1n(B)$
Oswin	$M_e = A \times (a_w/1-a_w)^B$	$1n(M_e) = 1n(A) + B1n(a_w/1-a_w)$
Smith	$M_e = A - B \times 1n(1-a_w)$	$M_e = A - B1n(1-a_w)$
Halsey	$M_e = -(A/T \times 1n(a_w))^{1/B}$	$1n(-1n(a_w)) = 1n(A/T) - B \times 1n(M_e)$
Henderson	$M_e = (-1/A \times T \times 1n(1-a_w))^{1/B}$	$1n(-1n(1-a_w)) = 1n(A \times T) + B1n(M_e)$
GAB	$m/m_o = (C1Ka_w)/(1-Ka_w)(1-Ka_w + C1Ka_w)$	$(a_w/1-a_w) \times 1/M_e = 1 + Aa_w + B(a_w)^2$

M_e = equilibrium moisture content, % (d.b.), m_o = monolayer moisture content, a_w = water activity, T = temperature; A, B, C, and K are constants.

Table 1. Statistical parameters computed for Henderson's equation.^a

Temperature (°C)	R ^e	SE ₂	p	s
<i>Rough rice</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9979	0.0237	4.9641	0.4095
20 (desorption)	0.9948	0.0331	5.7493	0.4783
30 (adsorption)	0.9977	0.0250	5.2291	0.3010
30 (desorption)	0.9977	0.0251	5.2715	0.2357
40 (adsorption)	0.9899	0.0558	7.6946	0.8303
40 (desorption)	0.9953	0.0352	5.9828	0.5682
<i>Brown rice</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9994	0.0093	3.1245	0.1305
20 (desorption)	0.9960	0.0251	5.2788	0.3315
30 (adsorption)	0.9859	0.0508	7.8132	0.5572
30 (desorption)	0.9776	0.0598	8.5309	0.7026
40 (adsorption)	0.9900	0.0454	6.8859	0.7269
40 (desorption)	0.9902	0.0427	6.6738	0.6718
<i>3.8% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9972	0.0235	5.0352	0.3737
20 (desorption)	0.9998	0.0050	2.4068	0.0850
30 (adsorption)	0.9968	0.0255	5.5695	0.3177
30 (desorption)	0.9970	0.0228	5.4673	0.3104
40 (adsorption)	0.9991	0.0131	3.8546	0.2079
40 (desorption)	0.9979	0.0198	4.7039	0.3077
<i>6.6% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9996	0.0081	3.0446	0.1335
20 (desorption)	0.9923	0.0338	5.7109	0.4279
30 (adsorption)	0.9877	0.0549	7.4310	0.9935
30 (desorption)	0.9835	0.0552	7.6346	0.9665
40 (adsorption)	0.9958	0.0320	5.8086	0.4939
40 (desorption)	0.9952	0.0294	5.5697	0.4641
<i>10.3% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9892	0.0429	6.9858	0.4655
20 (desorption)	0.9817	0.0497	7.5638	0.6273
30 (adsorption)	0.9819	0.0645	9.1193	0.7998
30 (desorption)	0.9752	0.0637	8.6034	0.8722
40 (adsorption)	0.9851	0.0622	7.6785	0.6956
40 (desorption)	0.9973	0.0221	5.7347	1.0400

^aR^e = coefficient of determination, SE₂ = standard error, p = mean relative percentage deviation, and s = root mean square deviation.

Table 2. Statistical parameters computed for GAB's equation.^a

Temperature (°C)	R ^e	SE ₂	p	s
<i>Rough rice</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9936	0.0006	3.9883	0.2612
20 (desorption)	0.9990	0.0003	2.9043	0.1165
30 (adsorption)	0.9936	0.0008	4.7826	0.2228
30 (desorption)	0.9984	0.0003	3.5050	0.1175
40 (adsorption)	0.9885	0.0009	4.3692	0.3356
40 (desorption)	0.9917	0.0008	4.7374	0.3099
<i>Brown rice</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9980	0.0004	3.6122	0.1939
20 (desorption)	0.9978	0.0004	3.9362	0.2375
30 (adsorption)	0.9972	0.0006	4.5757	0.2252
30 (desorption)	0.9952	0.0008	5.4132	0.3315
40 (adsorption)	0.9971	0.0005	3.9738	0.2139
40 (desorption)	0.9988	0.0003	3.4296	0.1473
<i>3.8% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9986	0.0003	3.2353	0.1382
20 (desorption)	0.9989	0.0003	3.3169	0.1758
30 (adsorption)	0.9953	0.0007	4.6853	0.2709
30 (desorption)	0.9963	0.0006	4.6299	0.2771
40 (adsorption)	0.9995	0.0002	2.3235	0.0840
40 (desorption)	0.9977	0.0004	3.1643	0.2108
<i>6.6% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9975	0.0004	3.8472	0.2250
20 (desorption)	0.9963	0.0006	4.9695	0.3102
30 (adsorption)	0.9938	0.0007	4.3361	0.2854
30 (desorption)	0.9998	0.0003	2.9866	0.1748
40 (adsorption)	0.9997	0.0004	3.4870	0.1818
40 (desorption)	0.9977	0.0004	2.5486	0.0908
<i>10.3% milled</i>				
20 (adsorption)	0.9961	0.0007	5.1185	0.2481
20 (desorption)	0.9976	0.0005	4.8273	0.2713
30 (adsorption)	0.9940	0.0008	4.8769	0.2995
30 (desorption)	0.9934	0.0008	5.6662	0.4186
40 (adsorption)	0.9889	0.0009	5.4052	0.3466
40 (desorption)	0.9977	0.0004	8.1920	0.9818

Partitioning of high-density grains and its implication in a rice selection program

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One approach to break the yield barrier in irrigated rice yields is to increase the number of high-density (HD) grains panicle⁻¹. Previous work reveals that yield potential can be raised by 30% with more HD grains panicle⁻¹. HD grains are fully filled grains with a specific gravity of 1.20 and above. Grain filling is generally superior in primary branches compared with secondary branches in the panicle. Therefore, HD

grains panicle⁻¹(HDGP) must be partitioned into its components: number of primary branches (PB) panicle⁻¹, number of secondary branches (SB) panicle⁻¹, number of HD grains on primary branches (HDGPB), number of HD grains on secondary branches (HDGSB), HD grain index on primary branches (HDIPB), HD grain index on secondary branches (HDISB), and HD grain index panicle⁻¹

(HDIP). These traits should be related to the end product, grain yield panicle⁻¹ (GYP).

We studied the components of HD grains in five short-duration rice varieties in an experiment conducted during 1997 kharif in a randomized block design with five replications. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of each variety were planted in a 5 × 4-m² plot and at a spacing of 15 × 10 cm.